

Original Articles

Bearers of Wind and Floodwaters: A Historical Geography of Damage Caused by Typhoons *Juaning* (2011), *Nina* (2016), and *Rolly* (2020) on the Infrastructure and Other Assets of Tabaco City, Albay, Philippines

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Abstract: The Philippines has experienced the most incidents of disasters caused by natural hazards in the 20th century, and it is one of the countries most at risk of being exposed to damaging winds and downpours brought about by typhoons (Warren, 2016). Among all Philippine provinces, it is the Province of Albay along the southeastern portion of Luzon that suffers the most damage from tropical cyclones. However, in Albay itself, its northern portion is the most susceptible to suffer floods emanating from overflowing rivers, storm surges, mudflows, and damage to infrastructure and property that result from cyclone visitations.

This study seeks to provide an account of the destruction inflicted by three typhoons on Tabaco City, the premier local government of Northern Albay, in 2011, 2016, and 2020. Using the city government's damage reports from these storms and combining these with Geographic Information Systems, this paper will provide a story and geographic rendering of how these specific climatic hazards wreaked havoc on the infrastructure of Tabaco, as well as influenced the repairs that were conducted in the aftermath of these storms.

Keywords: Historical Geography, HGIS, Typhoon and Infrastructure studies.

1. Introduction

Tabaco City is one of 18 local government units that make up the Province of Albay, a region located along the southeastern portion of the Philippines' Luzon Island that is frequently exposed to the rain and winds brought by typhoons (Uy et al., 2011: 139). Albay is hit by 3 to 5 typhoons annually, and particularly vulnerable to such extreme meteorological events is Tabaco City, which faces the Pacific Ocean.

Figure 1 - Situational map of Tabaco City.

Over the past decade, three particular tropical cyclones caused significant damage to Tabaco's infrastructure. These events include the passing of Typhoons *Juaning* (Tropical Storm Nock-Ten) in 2011, *Nina* (Typhoon Nock-Ten) in 2016, and *Rolly* (Typhoon Goni) in 2020.

While a rather weak storm that had a wind speed of only 75 kph, *Juaning* dumped 12 inches of rain on Albay – the equivalent to 10% of what the province receives annually – that led to floods, landslides, lahar flows, and impassable roads that affected 100,000 people (Salaverria, 2011) and country-wide infrastructure damage amounting to PhP 1.2B (Reliefweb, 2011). Known as the worst Christmas typhoon to hit the Philippines in half a century, Super Cyclone *Nina* in 2016 brought winds with speeds of 103–155 mph and seven (7) inches of rain on Christmas Day alone (Lam, 2016; Reliefweb, 2017). So damaging was its passing that the Albay Provincial Government declared a state of calamity in order to quickly access more funds for relief and recovery. In Tabaco, many upended electric posts served as proof of the typhoon's impact (Buan, 2017; DW.Com, 2016; Sayat, 2016).

Finally, Super Typhoon *Rolly*'s winds and rain caused major damage on the Bicol Region, including Albay province on the morning of All Saints' Day of 2020 (1 November). Unfortunately for Tabaco City, this Signal Number 5 cyclone, with winds of 225 kph and gusts up to 310 kph, made landfall on the locality's territory itself, pummeled its environs for six hours, and left destroyed infrastructure, massive floods, and landslides in its wake. Albay's provincial Governor Al Francis Bichara even described his jurisdiction as being "battered" by the said typhoon. In the Bicol Region, thousands of hectares of rice and corn land were classified as damaged, while infrastructure losses were estimated at PhP 11 billion (Enano et al., 2020).

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So significant was the harm inflicted by these typhoons that the Tabaco City Government’s Engineering Office (TCGEO) and the Department of Public Works and Highways’ District 1 Engineering Office (DPWHDEO) had collected information and produced detailed damage and repair reports in relation to these events. The gathering and arranging of the collected information into usable databases, the generation of maps, and analysis of such information serve as the main bases of this paper.

2. Research Questions

The content and quality of the available damage, repair, rehabilitation, and construction of infrastructure as a result and response to the three aforementioned typhoons provided the researchers with opportunities to produce data that can be mapped and studied to answer many questions. In the end, however, the team decided to focus on the rendering of information that could help answer the following questions:

1. How much was spent by the city and national government for infrastructure repair and rehabilitation, respectively, during the aftermath of Typhoons Juaning (2011), Nina (2016), and Rolly (2020)?
2. Are there spatial patterns in terms of both the damage caused by these typhoons on Tabaco City’s barangays and the areas prioritized for fund disbursement by the city and national governments in the repair of the city’s infrastructure? And
3. Which places in Tabaco City and what types of infrastructure are constantly being damaged by these typhoons?

3. Methodology

Database

The approach of the authors in gathering and rendering information that would be useful for analysis was quite straightforward. The authors communicated with TCGEO to assess what types of data could be collected from the latter. The latter then sent via email Excel files containing details of the damage on the city’s infrastructure, the amount of funds needed for repairs, and the local government funds that were actually utilized for such rehabilitation work. In addition, the researchers were also able to access yearly infrastructure work outlays for Albay that were sourced from the Philippine national government through the Albay’s DPWHDEO.

Given these data, the Tabaco City Government’s practice of dividing its 47 *barangays* or villages into *población* (city center), suburban, upland, and island ecosystem clusters, and the collection of village census data for the past 2010 and 2015 census years (PSA, 2011, 2016, 2021), the authors proceeded to produce databases that could be rendered into GIS maps for the following:

- a) Damaged infrastructure by type (i.e., schools; flood control; roads, spillways, and bridges; covered courts; evacuation areas; etc.) and costs that were associated with the three typhoons (TCGEO, 2016);
- b) Actual funds disbursed by the Tabaco City Government for repairs and rehabilitation (TCGEO, 2016); and
- c) Actual funds provided by the National Government for the reparation of particular facilities (DPWH Albay, 2020).

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These databases were then used as inputs for the generation of maps that served as the material for our analysis.

Spatial Analysis

In understanding the spatio-temporal patterns that may arise from the different databases gathered, the researchers classified the 47 barangays of Tabaco city based on its ecological attribute. The classification of barangays is divided into *población* (city center), suburban, upland, and island barangays as shown in figure 2. This classification was developed to better understand the damages brought about by the identified typhoons and the financial flow of reconstruction from the local government and the national government.

Figure 2 - Ecosystem classification of Tabaco’s 47 barangays.

4. Findings

Temporal and Spatial Patterns of Damages Caused by Typhoons

The value of public facilities losses in Tabaco City that were caused by particular tropical cyclone incidents have clearly increased over time. From only P75.2 million (\$1 USD = P51) that resulted from the onslaught of Typhoon Juaning, the value of the facilities damaged by Typhoon Nina five years later in 2016 more than doubled to P170.8 million. In the aftermath of Typhoons Rolly and then Ulysses in late 2020, the destruction wreaked by the two events on the city’s infrastructure was pegged at P1.83 billion, roughly 10 times the value (before inflation) of cyclones Juaning and Nina combined (See Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Value of Infrastructure Damage Caused per Typhoon.

The distribution of infrastructure losses in Tabaco's barangays has been uneven. As shown in Figure 4 below, it was the suburban barangays outside the city center that had facilities that were in need of repair or replacement. In particular, these included villages such as San Carlos, San Vicente, San Lorenzo, Matagbac, Cabangan, San Ramon, and San Lorenzo. Barangays along the city's uplands were the second group of settlements whose public structures were badly hit by typhoons. It should be noted that most river systems emanate from these upland and suburban areas, and this implies that the surge in water levels may have compromised a significant number of public works in these sites.

Figure 4 - Distribution of Public Works Damage by Barangay Type (Philippine Pesos).

Spatial Distribution of Government Post-Typhoon Infrastructure Expenditures

A visual assessment of Figures 5 and 6 reveal the differences in the geographic distribution of facilities projects that were given appropriations by the Tabaco City Government (TCG) as well as that of the national government (NG). TCG allotted 2/3 of its infrastructure repair funds from 2012 to 2019 on its upland barangays that overlap or proximate to the Mayon Volcano. On the other hand, the national government provided money for public facilities repairs and rehabilitation in Tabaco, by ecosystem, was more equally divided between its more populated suburban villages (47%) and upland barangays (42%), with the remaining 11% appropriated for its geographically compact and demographically dense urban center. It is interesting to note that both local and national governments did not provide any allotments for infrastructure repairs in the city's island villages. In terms of infrastructure or development fund allocations, national government outlays have always been much larger than the ones disbursed by local governments. Such is the case as majority of government revenues are collected at the national level. Republic Act 7160 or the Local Government Code of 1991, allows and encourages local governments to assess taxes in order to increase their budgets that could be used for development purposes. Unfortunately, up to the present, most local government units, such as Tabaco City, are still dependent on the national government's annual allotments for them to deliver basic services to their constituents.

Figure 5 - Spatial distribution of infrastructure repair and rehabilitation funds of the Tabaco City Government, 2012-19.

Figure 6 - Spatial distribution of infrastructure repair and rehabilitation funds of the National Government, 2012-19.

Geographic Pattern of Infrastructure Damage, 2011-2016

Clearly, the brunt of the cost of infrastructure damage has concentrated in the city's uplands, followed by the suburban settlements. This explains the significant funds poured by both the local and national governments for the repair, rehabilitation, and replacement of public facilities (See Figures 7a and 7b). There is, however, a clear spatial change in the distribution of repair funds provided by the NG over time. In Typhoon Juaning, the bulk of infrastructure rehabilitation was focused on Tabaco's uplands. By 2016, however, not only had the value of infrastructure expenditures quadrupled. Majority of these funds were concentrated on a wider geographic area to include the city's suburbs (See Figures 8a and 8b).

Figure 7a - Distribution of national and city government infrastructure expenditures during Typhoon Juaning 2011.

Figure 8b - Distribution of national government infrastructure expenditures during Typhoon Nina 2016.

The Tabaco City Government, on the other hand, was quite consistent as to where it poured the majority of its available infrastructure repair funds. In 2011, 76% of the city's facilities repairs budget was used in its upland barangays. After Typhoon Nina in 2016, the allocation for Tabaco's far-flung villages nearly doubled in amount but its percentage share of the total rehabilitation budget went down to 62% (See Figures 9a and 9b).

Figure 7b - Distribution of national and city government infrastructure expenditures during Typhoon Nina 2016.

Figure 9a - Distribution of city government infrastructure expenditures during Typhoon Juaning 2011.

Figure 8a - Distribution of national government infrastructure expenditures during Typhoon Juaning 2011.

Figure 9b - Distribution of city government infrastructure expenditures during Typhoon Nina 2016.

Most Damaged and Repeatedly Damaged Infrastructures
Based on the records provided by the Tabaco City Government, school buildings were the government structures that were likely to be harmed by the ill-effects

of typhoon-caused powerful winds and water surges. Nearly half (43%) of the value of infrastructure needing repair were educational facilities. These are followed by the impacts of storms on river-based flood control projects, which accounts for a third of infrastructure losses (33%), and essential repairs needed on roads, bridges and spillways (19%). Combined, these developmental, protective, and transport facilities account for 95% of Tabaco City’s public works losses due to extreme meteorological events (See Figure 10).

Cost of Damage (PHP) by Infrastructure Type

Figure 10 - Cost of Damage by Infrastructure Type.

School facilities may have been the public buildings most in dire need of repair and rehabilitation in the aftermath of typhoons, but these are by no means the most repeatedly damaged nor the costliest to repair. Given their being located within or near river systems that usually get inundated and receive rocks and other debris during tropical cyclones, river or flood control suffered the most significant and periodic harm. Of the roughly half a billion pesos (P500 million) of valued repeat damage on government structures, flood prevention facilities accounted for 70% of the said amount. The repeated structural harm on school facilities accounted for only 21% of the cost, while roads, spillways and bridges were the sites for only 10% of the ascertained recurring damage (See Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Distribution of Total Cost for Repeatedly Damaged Public Facilities.

These aforementioned trends, particularly with respect to infrastructure losses, give us reason to reflect. If flood control projects require significant repairs on a periodic basis, this implies that such undertakings have been normalized as accepted maintenance work that, in the long run, may be too costly to continue as a mitigation measure. Perhaps newer interventions such as green infrastructure or the relocation of communities to safer

areas should be considered. With respect to the impacts suffered by Tabaco City’s school buildings and facilities, the undesirability of such a learning environment could well have reduced the time spent on learning and the quality of education experienced by the city’s young population. These learning scenarios would likely have had an effect on the productivity and future economic prospects of those who were students in these institutions from 2011 to 2020.

5. Analysis

Build Back Better

There is no denying that Tabaco City’s infrastructures that have been damaged by periodic typhoons have been the object of seemingly cyclical rehabilitation and repair. With millions of Pesos having been spent on these public facilities, one might ask: Are they building better? Perhaps not.

Preliminary data indicates that repeatedly broken and ravaged public works have been the focus of much restoration funding. Yet despite the total value of the rehabilitation of infrastructure costing double than the damage inflicted by typhoons, these facilities are still repeatedly wrecked by flood and wind. Initial analysis suggests that government spending towards disaster recovery and reconstruction needs to be examined. This analysis could be linked to the ongoing effort of implementing the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR) especially on priority 4 which is about “Enhancing disaster preparedness for effective response and to ‘Build Back Better’ in recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction” (UNDRR, 2015). Priority 4 highlights the need for nations to make communities more resilient by addressing development issues found after a disaster hits. The study can provide the initial step in measuring the country’s efforts towards building back better and insights on how disaster mitigation infrastructure and other critical infrastructure are constantly impacted with disasters which begs the question of are we building back better.

National vs Local Government capacity

Clearly, in the case of Tabaco city government, the local government unit does not have sufficient funds to appropriate for all typhoon-related repairs, and it is the national government that has spent more on the rehabilitation of vital public facilities in Tabaco City. The study provides a snapshot of the large disparity of capacity by the national and local government to be instrumental in the recovery and reconstruction process despite the accountability being expected from the local government that directly serves the people in the front lines.

Interestingly, local government units would soon receive a larger budget due to the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling that allots more resources for the local government unit (Constitutional Reform Movement, 2020). With this new ruling it will be interesting to see how recovery and reconstruction expenditures will evolve as well as the quality of disaster recovery and reconstruction projects when local government units gain access to bigger resources.

6. Observations and Potential Directions

Statistical and spatial data based from the Tabaco City and Philippine National Governments' damage and repair documents reveal several realities. Tabaco's upland and urban areas have been the most affected by the devastating power of winds and floodwaters brought about by the Typhoons Juaning, Nina, and Rolly. While these aforementioned ecosystems have been the object of much attention and structural rehabilitation, Tabaco's Island barangays seem to have been largely ignored in terms of typhoon-related infrastructure repair.¹ In terms of the distribution of public works rehabilitation funds, the city government of Tabaco has concentrated their resources in its uplands - the area where many waterways emanate - while the more monied national government has roughly allotted the same amount of resources in both the study area's uplands and suburban settlements which are areas found to be the most affected by the three typhoons.

Flood control works and schools have been the public facilities most frequently damaged by typhoons. Sadly, despite the increased amount of funding and repeated rehabilitation, these two types of structures have repeatedly suffered adverse impacts from these storms even as the national government has allocated funds that more than makes up for the damage caused by such events.

Potential Directions

In addressing the continuing impacts of typhoons to Tabaco City it will be good to assess the local and national government's strategy towards building back better. Infrastructure design that utilizes more sustainable and cost-effective materials should be analyzed compared to the traditional infrastructure design. This can also be coupled with an extensive review of the city's land use and development plans to identify other possible mitigation strategies, such as resettlement of households in hazard areas.

To clearly address the initial findings of this study, it is imperative that more extensive research be conducted to better establish the baseline aimed at financing these critical infrastructures. In developing such a baseline, coordination between the national and local government is an important aspect to strategically implement cost-effective disaster recovery and reconstruction efforts. Moreover, more detailed analyses should be undertaken on the following: a) "recovery cost" for infrastructure projects (i.e., preventive and maintenance solutions), b) environmental factors and their relationship with infrastructure damages and recovery costs, and c) national government expenditures as opposed to estimated damages.

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¹ Again, we can only work with the data provided to them. One of the researchers, who is a local of Tabaco, could argue that the island communities of the city have also
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